

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Training, work ability, organizational commitment and employee performance

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Abstract

This research is based on the not yet optimal performance of the South Padang sub-district office staff which is characterized by inappropriate targets and realization of performance. Based on the 7 target indicators of employee performance with targets from agency programs of 100, on average only 84% is realized. Based on this, there are three factors that are suspected of causing this including training, work ability and organizational commitment. So, this study aims to see the effect of (1) Training on the performance of South Padang Sub-district Office employees (2) Work ability on the performance of South Padang sub-district office employees (3) Organizational commitment to the performance of South Padang Sub-District Office employees (4) Training, work ability and organizational commitment have a joint effect on the performance of employees in the South Padang District Office.

The population in this study were all employees of the South Padang sub-district office of 38 people. The technique of determining the number of samples using total sampling. The data analysis technique uses multiple regression by fulfilling the requirements of the classical assumption test for normality, and multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity.

The results of this study indicate that (1) Training provide a positive significant influence on the performance of employees of the South Padang Sub-District Office (2) Work ability has a positive influence on the Performance of South Padang District Office Employees (3) Organizational commitment has a negative influence on the performance of employees of the Padang Selatan sub-district office (4) Training, employability and organizational commitment jointly have a positive effect on the performance of employees of the South Padang District Office.

Keywords: Performance; Training; Work Ability; Organizational Commitment

1. Introduction

Employees are the most important asset for an agency. Without the presence of employees, agency activities cannot run as they should. In order for employees to work well, good human resource management is needed. Human resource management, namely the science and art of managing the relationships and roles of the workforce so that they are effective and efficient in helping the realization of agency, employee and community goals (Hasibuan, 2020). Human resource management is a planning, organizing, coordinating, implementing and supervising the procurement, development, remuneration, integration, maintenance and segregation of workforce in order to achieve organizational goals. Human resource management can also be defined as a management and utilization that is maximally developed in the world of work to achieve organizational goals and the development of individual employees (Mankunegara, 2016).

The job of an employee is a job that devotes himself in the field he is involved in and has knowledge and skills in that field for certain types requiring authority to make efforts to optimize work. This work is certainly not easy and time-

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consuming where a job has tasks in a few hours, in other words this job has a busy time both morning, afternoon and evening in carrying out services to the community.

An agency can operate well if the performance of its employees is also good. Performance is the result or level of success of a person as a whole during a certain period in carrying out tasks compared to various possibilities, such as work standards, targets or goals or predetermined criteria that have been mutually agreed according to (Rivai, 2019). In order to encourage the creation of accountability for the performance of government agencies as one of the prerequisites for creating a good and trustworthy government, it is necessary to organize a Government Agency Performance Accountability System (SAKIP) that integrates planning, programming, budgeting, implementation of programs and activities, as well as evaluation, which then set forth in the form of performance reporting.

South Padang Sub-District Office as an element of local government administration whose function is to carry out coordination, organize the formulation of city government policies, prepare information regarding the Sub-District Office area as material for preparing City Government policies, Delegation of some of the Mayor's authority, Fostering state ideology and national unity, implementing community empowerment, the implementation of general government tasks, the implementation of operational coordination of technical implementing units of the Services, Agencies, Offices, Government Administration Organizers, Management of Apparatus Resources, Finance, Infrastructure Facilities. The sub-district office is a regional apparatus that has a work area led by the sub-district head who is under and responsible to the Mayor through the Regional Secretary.

Table 1 The Average Performance Score of South Padang District Office Employees

No	Target	Performance Average Value Per Individual		
		2020	2021	2022
1	Increased community satisfaction with District services	88	85	75
2	Increased community participation in sub-district development	80	78	73
3	Increasing Governance, Public Services and Community Empowerment in the District	85	80	80
	Average	84	81	76

Source: Administrative Office of South Padang District Head

However, during the last 2 years there has been a decline in the performance of employees in the agency. Table 1 shows the performance achievements of the programs/activities carried out by employees of the Padang Selatan District Office for the period 2021 to 2022. Based on table 1 data above, it can be seen that the performance South Padang sub-district office employees from 2021 to 2022 will decrease. On average performance South Padang sub-district office employees in 2021 it will reach 81%, down from the previous year which reached 81%.

Based on Table 1 above, it can be concluded that the level of target efficiency is low. According to Anthony (2017) efficiency is an internal process or resource needed by an organization to produce one unit of output because if the resulting output fails to contribute to achieving organizational targets, then the organization is not effective. Efficiency as an organizational responsibility, where the organization must be able to achieve its goals optimally. Low performance This employee resulted in the difficulty of achieving the vision and mission of the South Padang sub-district office.

The low employee performance is thought to be caused by training, work ability, and organizational commitment. This is also in accordance with the opinion expressed by Hessel (2017) which states that several factors that can affect organizational performance are training, work ability, and organizational commitment.

From the observations it was found that there was no evaluation of the results of the training. One important point that supports employee performance is training. This is in accordance with the theory which says that the purpose of training is to improve performance and in turn will increase competitiveness (Tjiptono, 2017). Training is an activity of an agency that intends to be able to improve and develop attitudes, behavior, skills and knowledge of employees, in accordance with the wishes of the agency concerned (Alex, 2015).

The effect of training on performance has been investigated by previous researchers such as (Kharisma, 2017), (Khasanah, 2016), (Setiawan, 2015) And (Sendawula, et al 2018) who concluded that training has a significant effect on employee performance. When employees are given training there will be an increase in employee competence. Increasing competence will have an impact on improving employee skills. Of course this condition will be able to affect the increase in employee performance. Vice versa, if employees are not given training then there will be no increase in employee competence. This will not have an impact on improving employee performance.

In addition, from the results of the data in table 1, it can be seen that the employee's performance is also not optimal due to limited work ability in terms of technology. Work ability is also a factor that affects performance. This is in accordance with the opinion which states that the factors that influence performance are ability and motivation (Mankunegara, 2016). Work ability is a result of work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skill, experience and sincerity as well as time (Hasibuan, 2017). Meanwhile, ability (ability) is an individual capacity to do various tasks in a job according to (Robbins, 2019). This opinion has also not been proven empirically, especially in the South Padang sub-district office.

The results of previous research also show that work ability can have a positive impact on performance. The results of this study found by Hariadi, (2018), Khasana, (2016), Rachmadani, (2015), Setiawan, (2015), And Afrizal, et al (2020). The conclusion from this research is that if the employee's work ability increases, the employee's ability, both technical and non-technical, will get better. Basically this condition will be able to provide a positive effect on improving employee performance. Conversely, if the employee's work ability is low, the employee's performance will also be low.

Another factor that can affect employee performance is organizational commitment. This is in accordance with the opinion which states that the outcomes of organizational commitment are high performance, low employee turnover and low absenteeism (Luthans, 2016). Organizational commitment as a degree to which individuals identify with and engage with their organization and/or do not want to leave it (Greenberg, J., & Baron, 2017). Organizational commitment or employee loyalty is the degree to which employees identify with the organization and want to continue to actively participate in it (Meyer, 1984).

In line with the theory above, the results of previous research also show that strong organizational commitment will encourage better employee performance because employees have high determination and loyalty so they want to work well. Conversely, a lack of organizational commitment will reduce employee performance because employees feel disloyal and disloyal to the organization. Thus the performance will not be optimal. The findings of this study are concluded by Catherine, (2012), Hariadi, (2018), Handayani, (2014), Winna, (2013), And (Vipraprastha, et al, 2018).

Based on the phenomenon of the problems and the results of previous previous research, this study tries to develop and analyze the influence of training variables, work ability and organizational commitment on performance with the title Training, Work Ability, Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance (Case Study of South Padang District Office)

2. Material and methods

The population in this study were all employees of the South Padang sub-district office, totaling 38 people.

The technique for taking this sample uses a total sampling technique (overall sample), total sampling is a sampling technique where the number of samples is the same as the population (Sugiyono, 2017). The reason for taking total sampling is because according to (Sugiyono, 2017) the total population is less than 100, the entire population is used as a research sample. So the sample in this study was taken from all members of the population, namely employees of the South Padang Sub-District Office who were also as many as 38 people

Testing the hypothesis in this study using multiple regression analysis. Multiple regression analysis aims to determine the causal relationship between the variables that affect the variables that are affected. With the multiple regression equation model as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + e$$

Where:

Y = Performance
a = Intercept constant
X1 = Training

X2 = Work Ability
 X3 = Organizational Commitment
 b1, b2, b3.= Regression Coefficient
 e = Error Term

3. Results

3.1. Classic assumption test

3.1.1. Normality test

This normality test is used by the author to test the normality of the regression model. Testing is done by using the method *kolmogorov-smirnovtest* for each variable. The regression model is normally distributed if the Kolmogorov-Smirnov sign value for each variable is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. The results of the normality test can be seen in table 2.

Table 2 Normality Test Results

		Y	X1	X2	X3
N		38	38	38	38
Normal Parameters	Means	50.9250	39.7500	47.2750	31.5750
	std. Deviation	2.76783	2.97640	3.53726	2.45876
Most Extreme Differences	absolute	0.176	088	0.169	.119
	Positive	0.152	087	0.069	.106
	Negative	-0.176	-0.088	-0.169	-.119
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1,114	0.555	1,069	0.752
asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.167	0.918	0.203	0.624

Source: SPSS output results (2023)

From Table 2, which is a normality test, it can be seen that in the regression model, the confounding or residual variables have a normal distribution. This can be seen from the results of the sig value of the Performance variable (Y) which is $0.167 > 0.05$ training variable (X1) is $0.918 > 0.05$; work ability variable (X2) is $0.203 > 0.05$; organizational commitment variable (X3) is $0.624 > 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the variables for performance, training, work ability, and organizational commitment of the Padang Selatan Sub-District Office employees are normally distributed. The results of the normality test can be seen in table 2.

3.1.2. Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test is useful for testing whether the regression model found a correlation between independent variables. A good regression model should not have a correlation between the independent variables. If the independent variables are correlated, then these variables are not orthogonal. Orthogonal variables are independent variables whose correlation value between independent variables = 0 (Ghozali, 2017). Multicollinearity can be seen from the tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The way to find out whether there are deviations from the multicollinearity test is to look at the Tolerance and VIF values of each independent variable, if the Tolerance value is > 0.10 and the VIF value is < 10 , the data is free from multicollinearity symptoms, which can be seen in Table 3.

Based on the multicollinearity test in the table above, it can be seen that there is no relationship between the independent variables. So this research model is free from multicollinearity problems.

Based on the multicollinearity test in the table above, it can be seen that there is no relationship between the independent variables because the VIF values of all variables are < 10

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		tolerance	VIF
1	Training	0.919	1,088
	Work ability	0.906	1.104
	Organizational Commitment	0.978	1,023

a. Dependent Variable: Performance Source: SPSS output results (2023)

3.1.3. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in a regression model there is an inequality of variance from the residuals from one observation to another. If the variance from the residual of one observation to another observation remains, then it is called homoscedasticity and if it is different it is called heteroscedasticity. To detect the existence of heteroscedasticity in this study using the Scatter Plot test. In this test, if there is no clear pattern, such as the points spreading above and below the number 0 (zero) on the Y axis, then there is no heteroscedasticity. The test results can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

In Figure 1 it can be seen that there is no clear pattern and the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. The distribution of data points does not form a wavy pattern widening then narrowing and widening again. The distribution of data points is also not patterned, so this shows that the data in this study does not occur heteroscedasticity

3.2. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 4 Multiple Regression Equations

Coefficients a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	std. Error	Betas		
1	(Constant)	36,790	9,590		3,836	0.000
	Training	0.553	092	0.165	5,995	0.000
	Work ability	0.215	052	0.020	40.117	0.000
	Organizational Commitment	0.277	0.078	0.246	3,534	012

a. Dependent Variable: YSource: SPSS Output Results (2023)

This analysis is used to determine the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The magnitude of the influence of the independent variables with the dependent variable can be calculated through a multiple regression equation. Based on calculations via computer using the IBM SPSS for Windows Version 26.0 program.

The following is a recap table for the results of the regression coefficient, tcount, significance value, Fcount, and R Square (R²) value. The results can be seen in the above table:

Based on Table 4, the estimation model can be analyzed as follows:

$$Y = 36.790 + 0.553 (X1) + 0.215 (X2) + 0.277 (X3)$$

Based on the equation above it can be explained that:

- From the above equation it can be seen that there is a constant value of 36,790 which means that if training, work ability, organizational commitment are zero, then the value of the performance variable is 36,790. This means that the variables of training, work ability, organizational commitment contribute to improving the performance of employees of the South Padang Sub-district Office.
- The value of the training regression coefficient is positive 0.553. This means that if training increases by one unit, it will result in an increase in performance of 0.553 units.
- The value of the regression coefficient of work ability is positive, namely 0.215. This means that if work ability increases by one unit, it will result in an increase in employee performance by 0.215 units.
- The value of the regression coefficient of organizational commitment is positive, namely 0.277. This means that if organizational commitment increases by one unit, it will result in a decrease in employee performance by 0.277 units

3.3. Statistic test

3.3.1. Hypothesis Testing 1

The first hypothesis proposed shows that training partially has a positive effect on employee performance. Based on the results of the analysis of the t test, it is known that the significance level of the training variable is $0.000 < \text{the significance value } (0.05)$. Thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted so that the alternative hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted. This means that there is a significant positive influence between training on the performance of employees of the Padang Selatan District Office.

3.3.2. Hypothesis Testing 2

The second hypothesis proposed shows that work ability partially has a positive effect on employee performance. Based on the results of the analysis of the t test, it is known that the significance level of the working ability variable is $0.000 < \text{the significance value } (0.05)$. Thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted so that the alternative hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted. This means that there is a significant positive influence between work ability on the performance of employees of the Padang Selatan District Office.

3.3.3. Hypothesis Testing 3

The third hypothesis proposed shows that organizational commitment partially has a positive effect on performance. Based on the results of the analysis of the t test, it is known that the significance level of the organizational commitment variable is $0.012 < \text{dai significance value } (0.05)$. Thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted so that the alternative hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted. This means that there is a positive significant influence between organizational commitment on the performance of employees of the South Padang Sub-district Office.

3.4. F test (simultaneous)

3.4.1. Hypothesis Testing 4

The fourth hypothesis proposed shows that training, work ability, and organizational commitment together have a positive effect on employee performance. Based on the results of the analysis of the F test, it is known that the level of significance of the variable training, work ability, and organizational commitment is $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted so that the alternative hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted. This means that there is a jointly significant influence between training, work ability, and organizational commitment on the performance of employees of the Padang Selatan District Office. These results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5 F test results

ANOVA b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	MeanSquare	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27,143	3	9048	7,199	0.000a
	residual	271,632	34	7,545		
	Total	298,775	37			

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1; b. Dependent Variable: Y; Source: SPSS Output Results (2023)

3.5. Testing the Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Analysis of the coefficient of determination forward skills, soft skills and motivation on employee performance is carried out using the IBM SPSS for Windows Version 26.0 program with the SPSS output form as stated below:

Table 6 Adjusted Test Results *R Square*

Summary model b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.801a	0.641	0.612	2.74687

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2; b. Dependent Variable: Y; Source: SPSS Data Processing Results (2023)

Based on the results of the analysis, Adjusted R square is 0.612, this means that 61.2% of employee performance is influenced by the independent variables of training, work ability, work ability. While the remaining 38.8% is influenced by other variables outside the model.

4. Discussion

4.1. Influence Training on the Performance of South Padang District Office Employees

The results of this study indicate that training has a significant positive effect on the performance of employees in the South Padang sub-district office. This indicates that the training determines the performance of the Padang Selatan sub-district office staff. This means that the better and better the training received by employees in agencies, the employee's performance will improve.

From the results of this study, it appears that the training variable has a coefficient of 0.553, which means that training has the greatest influence of the other variables. This indicates that training can play a role in improving employee performance. If the Padang Selatan sub-district office wants to improve employee performance, it must increase the training provided to employees in agencies.

This is in line with opinion Alex, (2015) Education is an activity to increase one's general knowledge, including increasing mastery of theory and skills to decide on issues related to activities in achieving a goal (Heidjrachman, 2012) Training is an effort to improve the mastery of various skills and techniques for carrying out certain, detailed and routine work (Handoko, 2019).

Training and development is a unit that can be defined as a planned effort by the organization to improve the knowledge, skills and abilities of employees. But conceptual training and development can also change employee attitudes toward work. This is due to the employee's understanding of his work also changing, because a person's attitude has cognitive elements, namely belief and knowledge of an object as a result of his knowledge and beliefs, and the tendency to act towards the object, so that the knowledge obtained will be able to change a person's attitude. However, training can also be carried out specifically to change employee attitudes in an effort to increase work satisfaction and motivation when needed.

The results of this study are in line with Verra Nita's research (2016) which shows that training has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Kalasey agricultural technical training employees. Kharisma, (2017) the results

of his research also show that training has a significant effect on the performance of the Sarolangun Regency Education Office employees.

4.2. Influence Work Capability on the Performance of South Padang District Office Employees

The results of this study indicate that work ability has a significant positive influence on the performance of employees in the South Padang sub-district office. This indicates that the work ability of employees determines the performance of employees of the Padang Selatan sub-district office. This means that the better the work ability of employees in agencies, the better the performance of these employees.

From the results of this study, it appears that the variable work ability has a coefficient of 0.215, which means that work ability has a large influence. This indicates that work ability can play a role in improving employee performance. If the Padang Selatan sub-district office wants to improve employee performance, the agency must improve the work ability of employees in the agency.

This is in line with opinion Robbins, (2016) Ability shows the potential of people to carry out tasks or jobs. Ability is closely related to the physical and mental abilities possessed by people to carry out work (Wiger & Rettig, 2022)

Low employee ability will use greater time and effort than high employee ability to complete the job. Each type of work requires certain knowledge and skills and attitudes in order to carry out the task properly. Provides an understanding of ability as the mental and physical capacity to carry out various tasks (Greenberg, J., & Baron, 2017). Ability shows the potential of people to carry out tasks or jobs. That ability may or may not be utilized. Ability is closely related to the physical and mental abilities that people have to carry out work and not what they want to do (Gibsons, 2018).

The results of this study are in line with research Hariadi, (2018) which shows that work ability affects the performance of Klaten Education Office employees. Khasana, (2016) the results of his research also show that work ability has a significant effect on the performance of East Java Provincial Health Office employees.

4.3. Influence Organizational Commitment to the Performance of South Padang District Office Employees

The results of this study indicate that organizational commitment has a significant positive effect on the performance of employees of the South Padang sub-district office. This indicates that Organizational Commitment determines the performance of the Padang Selatan District Office employees. This means that the better and better the organizational commitment of employees in an agency, the better the performance of employees.

From the results of this study, it appears that the organizational commitment variable has a coefficient of 0.277, which means that organizational commitment has a large influence. This indicates that organizational commitment can play a role in improving employee performance. If the Padang Selatan sub-district office wants to improve employee performance, it must increase organizational commitment to employees in agencies.

This is in line with the opinion according to Luthans, (2014) Organizational commitment is the desire of some workers to remain members of the organization. Organizational commitment affects whether a worker stays as a member of the organization (is retained) or leaves to pursue other jobs (turns over). Colquitt, Le Pine, and Wesson (2011) organizational commitment or employee loyalty is the degree to which workers identify with the organization and want to continue to actively participate in it (Daft, 2011).

The results of this study are in line with research Handayani, (2014) which shows that there is a significant influence between organizational commitment on the performance of employees of the Tourism and Culture Office of Solok Regency. The results of this study are also in accordance with the research Winna, (2013) there is a significant influence between organizational commitment on the performance of employees of the Investment Service and One Stop Service in Klaten Regency.

4.4. Influence of Training, Employability, Organizational Commitment on the Performance of South Padang District Office Employees

The results of this study indicate that training, work ability, and work ability together have a significant influence on the performance of employees of the South Padang Sub-district Office. This indicates that training, work ability, work ability determine the performance of employees of the South Padang Sub-district Office. This means that increased training, work ability and organizational commitment will have an impact on improving employee performance.

This is in line with research, Hariadi, (2018), Vera Nita (2016), Handayani, (2014) which shows that there is a significant influence between training, work ability and organizational commitment on employee performance

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the testing and discussion of the hypotheses described in the previous chapter, several conclusions can be drawn that training has a positive influence on the performance of employees in the South Padang District Office. The highest average score is in grades 4.47 with a TCR of 89.47% which lies in statement 6 and is in the Good category. This gives an indication that the statement The training methods that are always used in training held by the company are in accordance with my character, position and age, the employees respond well.

For the work ability variable, it has a positive influence on the performance of the Padang Selatan sub-district office employees. The highest average score is in grades 4.42 with a TCR of 88.42% located in statements 5 and 6 are in the Good category. This gives an indication that the statement I always look for solutions myself when I face problems at work and Obstacles in a job are challenges for me that must be resolved properly and the employees respond well.

Furthermore, organizational commitment has a positive influence on the performance of employees of the South Padang District Office. The highest average value is in value 4.42 with a TCR of 88.42% located in statements 2 and 6 are in the Very Good category. This gives an indication that the statement I can adapt to the job given and Obstacles in a job are challenges for me that must be resolved properly and well responded by employees.

Training, work ability, work ability together have an influence on the performance of employees of the South Padang Sub-district Office. The highest average score is in grades 4.61 with a TCR of 92.11 which lies in statement 1 and is in the Very Good category. This gives an indication that the statement "The results of my work are satisfying to the leadership are well responded by employees."

Suggestion

Based on the results of the discussion analysis and some conclusions in this study, suggestions that can be given through the results of this study in order to get better results, namely:

- For training, it is suggested to agencies in order to improve the training provided to employees. Training will be able to make employees' hard skills and soft skills better. Of course, this condition will have an impact on the better performance of employees. The lowest average value lies in statements 2, 7 and 8 of 4.29 which are in the good category. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the quality of training indicators.
- For work ability, it is suggested to agencies to continue to improve employee work ability by providing skill forums, workshops, seminars and education improvement. The lowest average value lies in statement 8 of 4.11 which is in the Good category. Thus it is necessary to increase the dexterity of employees at work.
- For organizational commitment, it is suggested to agencies to be able to increase organizational commitment to employees by providing an understanding of the institution's values and knowledge of the history of the institution. The lowest average value lies in statement 4 of 4.21 which is in the good category. For this reason, it is necessary to increase the indicator of loyalty.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors contributed positively to the writing of this manuscript and there no conflict of interest as agreed to the content of this research.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individuals respondents included in the study.

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